

EU funds absorption for Romanian rural municipalities: a spatial distribution

Abstract

This study analyzes spatial differences on EU funds absorption for Romanian rural municipalities in relation to the 2014-2020 programming period. The absorption capacity of EU funds is measured by the volume of EU funds spent by inhabitant by each Romanian rural municipality. The results of the analysis highlight the importance of the territorial dimension when studying distribution of EU funds in the rural municipalities of Romania. Affiliation to a specific development region (NUTS2), county (NUTS 3) or a functional urban area (FUA) differentiates the volume of absorbed EU funds. Levels of fiscal capacity, locality development, experience with EU and State-Budget funding, together with population dynamics in 2021 compared to 2014 also distinguish between categories of municipalities with EU funds. In Romania, rural municipalities with higher levels of absorbed volume of EU funding are to a statistically higher extent from the development regions of Center, North-West, South West and West, from communes with no change or even increase of population between 2021 and 2014, from the highest quartile of fiscal capacity and with previous experience on EU funding in the preceding programming period. This article adds to the growing knowledge on territorial evidence and can be further used as a policy instrument in order to closer examine the intervention tools from the EU funding policy. In a systemic approach, the results of the analysis are valuable for design of integrated place-based strategies for EU, national and local level stakeholders, having as ultimate goal an improved quality of life for citizens living in rural areas.

Keywords: EU funds; rural municipalities; Romania; region; county.

1. Introduction

Romania became a member of the European Union in 2007. Since then, a substantial volume of EU funds has been available for a diverse set of potential beneficiaries, including rural municipalities. Although territory represents an important characteristics of EU funding policy design, a highly disaggregated analysis on the results of all sources EU funding is not the commonplace. This article is addressing this gap by providing research results on an extensive dataset of EU funding for all the rural municipalities in Romania.

The aim of this study is to identify and analyze spatial differences on EU funds absorption for Romanian rural municipalities in relation to the 2014-2020 programming period. The absorption capacity of EU funds is measured by the volume of EU funds spent by inhabitant by each Romanian rural municipality. The research area is Romania, and the research period is 2016-2021, corresponding to payments registered in the local budgets in relation to EU funds from the programming period of 2014-2020. Data have been processed¹ in order to allow comparisons between municipalities from Romania as well as, if the case occurs, municipalities from other EU countries. The absorption capacity is expressed in euro at constant prices 2010 per inhabitant and reflects the sum for the entire period of 2016-2021. The process of data management can be replicated in different spatial contexts in other EU member states, at the local administrative unit (LAU) level. Moreover, the publicly available database on which the current study is based upon can provide the grounds for further analyses and comparative approaches, subject to data availability.

Study's novelty rests on the analysis of spatial differentiation at the lowest disaggregated level, for the entire rural space in Romania. Whereas the national and regional (NUTS 2) levels are more addressed, less is known about the counties (NUTS 3) and even much less about the municipality (LAU) level. As at least partially EU funding policy aims at reducing disparities, spatial analysis of EU funds absorbed by municipalities becomes an essential tool for evidence-based policy making. Unlike some of the preceding examples, we explore this topic by analyzing actual payments done, instead of allocations, and, in addition, we add the annual absorbed funds into a global sum that would best reflect a multi-annual absorption capacity, in relation to the entire programming period.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 outlines some of the approaches on EU funds absorption from a territorial perspective. Section 3 presents general characteristics of rural municipalities in Romania, in order to better contextualize the paper's results against the national level frame of reference. Sources of data and analysis methods are presented in section 4, while results and discussion are put forward in Section 5, respectively Section 6. Last section, Section 7,

¹ See the subsection on Data aggregation, from Data and methods.

provides conclusive remarks and suggestions for next steps and further use of results analysis at the EU, national and local levels.

2. EU funds absorption: different approaches from a territorial perspective

Absorption capacity of EU funds has been studied at multiple layers – national (EU Member State), by operational programme (across the EU and/or member states), regional (NUTS 2 level), county (NUTS 3 levels) and, by the same vein as the current study, at the municipality level (LAU). It has been referred to both the timeframe before the EU funded projects/ programs actually start the process of implementation (as a type of ex-ante assessment), as well as during and upon completion of projects implementation.

At the member states level, a systemic view on the absorption capacity groups on the supply side the macro-economic conditions, co-financing capacity and administrative capacity, whereas the capacity of beneficiaries to prepare projects rests on the demand side (Sumpikova et al., 2006). Good governance and financial capacity have been identified as among factors differentiating levels of EU funds absorption between EU member states (Achim and Borlea, 2015), alongside administrative capacity (Marinas, Prioteasa, 2016, Țigănașu et al., 2018), government effectiveness and fighting corruption (Incaltarau et al., 2020) and high income levels (Tosun, 2014).² Under the same level, ex-ante assessments conducted for Romania on the absorption capacity indicated a rather early stage of preparations at the onset of the first programming period (Oprescu et al., 2006) and the need for integrating perspective between the European and national levels of operation (Cace et al., 2009).

At the regional level - several regional characteristics highlighting the presence of 'pro-cohesion' policies for disadvantaged areas (Collins et al., 2017), again the role of administrative capacity, which in its turn is influenced by political interference, government stability and political accountability (Milio, 2007), the importance of studying regional absorption capacity within the context of multilevel governance (Cunico et al., 2022), the high relevance of how the regional absorption capacity is actually computed, alongside how the political accountability is shared between the regions and the EU (Aivazidou et al., 2020), the significance of an integrated approach, including the public servants' motivations and the political salience of policies (Domorenok et al., 2021), the context of 'artificially created' NUTS 2 regions for absorbing EU funds (Maier et al., 2021).

A previous analysis performed at NUTS2 level differentiates the type of regions in the analysis of factors identified as determinants for EU funds absorption. The analysis differentiates between convergence regions (GDP per capita less than 75% of the EU average) and development regions (GDP per capita above 75% of the EU average). Labour force characteristics, decentralisation,

² In reference to a specific fund, European Regional Development Fund's (ERDF), for the 2000–06 programming period.

investments, institutional framework and infrastructure development count in this respect. Labour force characteristics are measured in reference to the educational level and unemployment rates prove to be a variable with a significant influence for successful absorption of EU funds in all NUTS 2 regions, while the institutional framework, measured in relation to good governance and control of corruption proves its importance especially in convergence regions (Kersan-Škabić, I. & Tijanić, L., 2017). Same factor, quality of governance, has been studied in relation to EU funds absorption measured at regional level as a standard deviation (differences between average at national level and disbursed amounts), for the Bulgarian context, in which regions are, similar to Romania, "there is no equivalent administrative territorial unit but only statistical regions" (Kalfova, 2019: 6).

At the county level, importance of contagion and diffusion territorial processes or to the significance of financing needs are highlighted in previous analyses (Maier et al., 2022). This analysis considers only the EU funds absorbed from the Common Agricultural Policy and managed through AFIR (Agency for Financing Rural Investments). It emphasizes the importance of spatial analyses, assimilated to contagion and diffusion, or a "longitudinal clusterization", from East to West. The paper concludes as favoring factors being located in the Western part of Romania and making use of more performant local institutions (Maier et al., 2022).

At the municipality level, beneficiary's capacity of initiating, conducting and successfully implementing EU funded projects can also be regarded as an input variable with an influence on the overall absorption capacity at the member states' or operational program's level (Boeckhout, 2002). Furthermore on the municipalities, earlier research identified a typology of success and passive municipalities (Cyburt, 2014), the role played by administrative capacity (Marin, 2015), the spatial position of municipalities regarding the main urban center in the subregion, level of their socio-economic development, local leadership (Cyburt, 2014), absorption and level of development of rural communities availability and characteristics of State Budget funding (Marin, 2021), residence area (Hochholdinger et al., 2021) or institutional arrangements (Maier et al., 2021), financial situation of local communities (Mirska, 2021), importance awarded in the EU policy to the specific needs, like demographic decline which affect rural areas (Weber et al., 2020).

A complex analysis of the development indicators of rural territorial units from Poland shows the importance of spatial attributes and the need to refine the allocation logic of the cohesion policy, in order to build the conditions for an improved use of local resources (Gospodarowicz, 2022). Size and proximity to the center are in particular emphasized as important factors in delineation of different lines of development in the rural areas, in the case of those who remain decoupled of the polycentric nature of the spatial structure (Gospodarowicz, 2022). For the same country context, the importance of local budget level, level of development and "degree of deagrarianisation" of local economies is mentioned in relation to spatial distribution of EU's Cohesion Policy (CP) at the level of rural areas (gmina/commune) (Komorowski, 2021).

A prior analysis on the determinants of EU funds absorption by communes in a Polish region draws attention to the importance of previous experience acquired when using EU funds as employees of mayoralities have the opportunity "of learning incomprehensible language of

programmatic documentation and complicated system of estimating the eligible costs" (Standar, 2010: 104). Same article underlines the importance of setting up a comprehensible prefunding system or ensuring access to credits – in their case, preferential credits from the fund managed by the Bank of National Economy (BGK) (ibid).

However, at the theoretical level the discussion needs to enlarge the perspective with concepts and relationships related to the characteristics of the funding environment - i) complexity – as complex knowledge required by the environment; ii) lack of stability or dynamism, measured by the rate of changes occurring in the environment and iii) resource availability - as the level of available resources in the environment, Sharfman and Dean (1991: 683). This theoretical lens assumes municipalities as open public organizations which influence and are influenced by the environment. Within this perspective, municipalities' absorption capacity can be influenced by many factors at macro and meso levels, among which the programming phase of EU funds for each implementation period plays a key role. The match between explicit or implicit local priorities and eligible funding lines at national level is not always met. In addition, even though this match is achieved, the co-funding rates cannot be supported for all needed and eligible funding objectives. Hence, one of the key questions is the application process in itself, which is not captured by the analyzed data. For instance, it is hard to say whether the 'white spots' presented in this article have actually tried to submit EU funded projects and/ or they have been eligible for specific EU funding lines. Moreover, some of the funding lines even offer 'pre-determined' projects, in which the idea of 'open competition' is not valid any more.

One approach that would capture a systemic view on external funds absorption and its relationship with the environment comes from the field of the sociology of organizations, with a view on the organizational effectiveness as „the ability of the organization, in either absolute or relative terms, to exploit its environment in the acquisition of scarce and valued resources" (Yuchtman, Seashore, 1967: 898). This capacity is assimilated to a "bargaining position" for the organization, or "a more general capability of the organization as a resource-getting system" (ibid.). Although the definition seems to be appropriate for the case of EU funding, it is still difficult to operationalize in an integrated model all types of environmental influences that exert impact on the organization. It can be the case that some of them – like resource availability can significantly influence both the annual absorption capacity (like the late opening of some of the Operational Programs), as well as the overall absorption capacity. Earlier research analyzed the importance of State budget funds from the largest State budget funded program (PNDL II) (Marin, 2021), especially for the county level. The current study considers absorption capacity as a process variable, in which previous experience in the first programming period (2007-2013) will be taken into consideration. Hence, as a process variable, it is difficult to establish causality, as it can be the case that in some instances, a good absorption capacity in preceding programming period can attract highly qualified human personnel which acts as a positive influence in the studied timeframe. It is still possible that some local administrative units can attract high volume of funds during 2007-2015, that require a high co-funding rate, which leaves little room for co-funding projects in the programming period of 2014-2020. A multi-annual plan of public investments can

contribute to solving this issue, as already stated in the national Fiscal Budgetary Strategy 2020-2022 (Ministry of Public Finance, 2019). Same problem is anticipated by a World Bank project on coordination of investment priorities, with an estimate on prudent capital expenditure margins for county councils (World Bank, 2016: 759). Another problem, also related to the fiscal capacity is that of sustainability of the implemented investment. In this sense, previous studies computed a specific index of financial sustainability in the context of investments conducted in the rural areas – in particular for the road and social infrastructure (World Bank, 2016).

Nonetheless, the most important questions rest on the impact of EU funds on the local development and on improving citizens' quality of life. This is in fact the key aspect around the relevance of studying this topic. Prior analyses conducted at the municipality level for the countries in Central and Eastern Europe show that there is a positive impact on the socio-economic local development, however it is difficult to state the impact's scale, especially given the long-term impacts of some of the EU-funded programs (Spychała, 2020). Additionally, similar to the EU funds absorption capacity, several factors have been identified in relation to the differentiated impact of EU funds, including the level of territorial capital (Fratesi and Peruca, 2014). Especially concerning NUTS 2 level, a recent study on Romania highlights the growing regional disparities, in association with a high absorption capacity of EU funds attributed mostly to capital cities (county seat municipalities) (Sandu, 2022).

This study is centered around characteristics at locality level and analyzes characteristics of the EU funds absorption in relation to the locality factors. However, the locality's absorption capacity is also in relation to the national, regional or county levels absorptions, to varying degrees. Yet, we do not take it into account in the model of analysis and can be subject to further upcoming analyses.

3. Research background: general characteristics of rural municipalities in Romania

This section briefly introduces key characteristics of the local public administration in Romania, in order to offer a contextualized understanding of the reporting of results in the next part of the paper.

The Romanian system of public administration is represented by a two-tier local government structure including 3,181 municipalities (3,180 municipalities plus the municipality of Bucharest, capital city) and 41 county councils.³ The set of 3,181 municipalities includes 2,862 rural

³ The open database on which the article performed analyses includes 3,187 cases of local public administration organizations, as it also covers the six districts from Bucharest, which are organized as separate municipalities from Bucharest. In fact, the six municipalities of Bucharest include a different set of responsibilities than the rest of municipalities in Romania. This is why they usually need a distinct analysis path in order to have meaningful results, especially if compared to the rest of urban municipalities in Romania.

municipalities,⁴ 217 towns and 102 cities.⁵ The local and county councils' representatives are elected. The members of the local councils (municipalities) are elected by secret ballot and by direct suffrage.

The legal framework does not include a statement on subordination relationships between the two levels of public administration – the county and the local councils. The Administrative Code states that the relationships between the local and county public authorities are based on the principles of local autonomy, legality, cooperation, solidarity, equal treatment and responsibility (art. 85, para 1). The same legal document affirms there are no subordination relationships between these two structures and that between them there are collaboration relationships (art. 85, para 2). However, the fundamental law of Romania, the text of the Constitution mentions that the county council represents the public authority in charge of coordinating the activity of rural and urban local councils, for the purpose of supplying county level public services.⁶ The mayors are the executive bodies of the local councils/ municipalities. The county council's leader is represented by the president of the county council.

The territorial structure of Romania's rural area is fragmented, with a substantial number of municipalities under or equal to 5,000 inhabitants. They represent more than one third of the population of the total number of 3,180 municipalities (excluding the capital city, the municipality of Bucharest). Moreover, data from the latest available Population Census (2011) show that about one quarter of the rural municipalities in Romania are under 2,000 inhabitants. It would be very useful to compare these population data with the updated census from 2022, in order to see the differences. Such a small size, of less than 2,000 inhabitants, can represent a significant challenge when applying for EU funding, especially in the case of public physical investments, like water and sewerage or sanitation.

The level of fiscal autonomy of Romanian rural municipalities significantly varies by development region (Table 1). The municipalities from the lower quartile of fiscal capacity (own revenues per inhabitant) are more likely to come from the North East and South West development regions. On the contrary, rural municipalities from the upper quartile of fiscal autonomy are to a significantly higher extent from the development regions of West, North-West, Center and Bucharest-Ilfov. These four development regions are precisely Romania's regions with the highest GDP per capita. In fact, measured against the EU-27 average, the development region of Bucharest-Ilfov is above the EU-27 value.⁷

Size of the local budget and level of fiscal autonomy are important not only for providing general public services, but also in particular for the topic of this study, for ensuring the co-financing part

⁴ Baneasa municipality from Constanta county has been a city until 2019, when it has been classified as a commune. In the current analysis we consider it as a rural locality.

⁵ Annex to Law no. 290/2018, Statistical situation documentary on administrative organization of Romania's territory.

⁶ Article 122 of the Romanian Constitution.

⁷ The only development region in Romania with a higher value than the EU-27 average. Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant in percentage of the EU27 (from 2020) average, Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices by NUTS 2 regions [NAMA_10R_2GDP], Eurostat database.

of EU funded projects. Communes placed in the upper quartile of fiscal capacity are more likely to cover the co-funding part of a large scale project, and therefore, attract a higher volume of EU funding. As can be seen from Table 1 all communes from the highest development region, Bucharest-Ilfov, are placed in the upper quartile of fiscal capacity. Noteworthy, Table 1 presents pre-pandemic levels of fiscal capacity, as average value of three years. It is possible that the level of rural fiscal capacity can be significantly different when computing an average value of 2020, 2021 and 2022.

Table 1. Fiscal capacity by development region, rural localities in Romania (%)

		Fiscal capacity				
		Lower quartile	Medium – low quartile	Medium – upper quartile	Upper quartile	Total
Development Region	North East	71.1	20.0	5.3	3.6	100
	South East	23.9	28.4	26.1	21.6	100
	South Muntenia	28.9	25.2	33.3	12.5	100
	South West	35.0	45.1	13.7	6.1	100
	West	5.0	13.9	28.5	52.7	100
	North West	7.4	32.8	31.8	28.0	100
	Center	*	19.3	40.1	38.9	100
	Bucharest-Ilfov	0	0	0	100	100
	Total (N)	788	757	700	617	2862
	Total (%)	27.5	26.5	24.5	21.6	100

Source: Author's calculations, based on the public information data on local budgets execution for all communes in Romania. Grey cells indicate significantly higher values (adjusted residuals). * Lower than 10 cases. Note: Fiscal capacity is measured as own revenues by inhabitant (in constant euro at 2010 prices, per inhabitant), average value for the years of 2016, 2017 and 2018.

Development regions in Romania are not part of the structure of the local public administration. Although we present results disaggregated by this territorial dimension, development regions in Romania are statistically constructed. They have been set up in relation to programming EU funds absorption, but it is important to note that in the case of Romania, unlike other EU countries, they do not match corresponding structures in the local public administration.

4. Data and methods

4.1 Data sources

The cumulative EU funds for the period of 2014-2020 represent financial data from the local budgets execution, as published by the Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration, Directorate for Local Fiscal and Budgetary Policies.⁸

4.2 Data aggregation

The process of data management included merging all the information for all the localities in Romania by assigning correct unique identification codes (SIRSUP, LAU 2 codes) for all municipalities for all the analyzed years. The entire process of data aggregation is presented in the technical description of the EU FAR open database.⁹ The category of EU funds from the programming period of 2014-2020 is registered as a distinct category in the local budgets'

⁸ http://www.dpfbl.mdrap.ro/sit_ven_si_chelt_uat.html.

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7460011>.

execution starting from 2016.¹⁰ Notably, all the information in the database presents payments (executed budget) and not allocations and it also includes all sources of EU funding, irrespective of the funding line (EFRD, ESF, but also Norwegian cooperation programs).

The key variable of the study is represented by the variable on total sum of EU funds, expressed as euro, in constant prices per inhabitant¹¹. The process of data management involved converting the sums reported by municipalities in lei at the end of each year into euro at constant 2010 prices per inhabitant. The exact steps and indicators for this process are described into the technical description of EU FAR database.

In earlier research, absorbed funds at national level and NUTS II level are aggregated by standard deviation, instead of sums, as a measure of regional policy efficiency (Kalfova, 2019), based on a localisation of the project at NUTS 3 level. However, the current paper uses funds from all EU funding lines, already localized at LAU level. It uses the summative approach of expenditures, also used in spatialization and harmonization of a large data set on the payments from the Common Agricultural Policy (Nicholas et al., 2021).

4.3 Data analysis

In this article, we use the term 'rural' in reference to the territorial organization of the country land. The detailed classification is openly available with the National Institute of Statistics.¹² Based on this classification there are currently 2,861 municipalities in the rural area of Romania (communes). Therefore, we did not take into consideration the classification of Local Administrative Units (LAU or communes) into three types of area, based on population density and used by Eurostat. According to this latter classification, rural areas correspond to thinly populated areas, namely more than 50% of the population lives in rural grid cells.¹³

Several predictors have been systematically tested in reference to the volume of absorbed EU funds – level of fiscal capacity (average value of own revenues in euro at constant 2010 prices per inhabitant), affiliation to development region, county and functional urban area, population dynamics in 2021 compared to 2014, EU funding in previous programming period 2007-2013 (as registered in the local budgets execution reports in 2016-2021), presence of a marginalized community, funding from State-budget programs, as well as level of development. A complete list of variables used in the analysis is available in the Annex of the article.

¹⁰ Nonetheless, this is also a cause of delay in approving the corresponding operational programs and certification of management authorities.

¹¹ Variable name in the database: [SUM_EU_2016_2021_inhab]. For values per each year, the following variables are available: [SUM_inhab_2016], [SUM_inhab_2017], [SUM_inhab_2018], [SUM_inhab_2019], [SUM_inhab_2020] and [SUM_inhab_2021].

¹² Tempo online database, indicator code [ADM101A]. <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table>

¹³ DEGURBA, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/degree-of-urbanisation/background>.

4.4 Limitations

It would be useful to have further disaggregation of data by type of accessed operational program, as the budgetary coding allows this refinement of data. The format of the budgetary reporting includes separate codes for funds from the European Fund for Regional Development, European Social Fund, Cohesion Fund, European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, European Fund for Fisheries, but also those corresponding to the European and Economic Space, as well as to other programs. Nevertheless, in the current format of budgets execution this information is not recorded by operational program.

Another limitation of the analysis is that it implicitly assumes a high degree of homogeneity among eligible conditions for accessing EU funds for rural municipalities, which in fact is not always the rule. For instance, the volume of EU funds is different according to the degree of development of the region (GDP per capita less or above than 75% of the EU average) they come from. Moreover, the municipalities from counties in the border regions can also benefit from an increased volume of funds through the territorial cooperation operational programs.

Another limitation of the database is related to missing information on the leaders of the municipalities throughout the analyzed period. The analyzed data are from the period of 2016-2021, yet Romania undergone general local elections in September-October 2020. It would be useful to know whether there has been a continuity in the mayor's position or not and whether the mayor's political affiliation changed or not. However, the current format of publicly display of data on local elections does not allow this type of analysis.

5. Results

5.1. General results

The peak of EU funds absorption by Romanian rural municipalities is registered for 2020. Table 2 shows that both the highest average value for 2020 as well as the greatest sum of EU funds absorbed, as the top value for the maximum level for the same year. Consequently, the largest standard deviation is registered again for 2020. In contrast, the low volumes absorbed in 2016 shows an early stage of preparations for contracting and implementing the projects corresponding to 2014-2020 programming period. Additionally, the commune with the highest level succeeded in absorbing almost double than the next highest value. In total for the whole period, in reference to the last variable in Table 2, less than 50 communes achieved an absorption volume of more than 1,000 euro in constant 2010 prices per inhabitant.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for the volume of EU funds absorbed by rural municipalities

	EU funds per inhabitant in						
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Sum_2016_2021
Mean	1.8	14.1	24.1	36.1	43.8	35.4	155.3
Median	0.0	0.0	0.3	7.1	7.5	3.2	45.9
Std. Deviation	17.8	55.9	62.1	70.2	93.6	82.3	242.8
Minimum	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maximum	353.3	1264.7	850.0	777.1	1862.2	1585.8	2517.8
Sum	5147.8	40252.3	68948.3	103460.8	125459.9	101338.4	444607.6
Number of cases	2862	2862	2862	2862	2862	2862	2862

Source: Authors' calculations based on EU FAR database. The values are expressed in euro at constant 2010 prices per inhabitant.

5.2. Characteristics of categories of EU funding in the rural areas

This section presents the results of the analysis, with a distinction between municipalities with zero funding from the programming period of 2014-2020 and those which succeeded in securing various levels of funding from the entire volume of EU funds available for Romania. In total, there are 462 municipalities considered as 'white spots' on EU funding for this timeframe, out of which 25 municipalities are from the urban area and 437 municipalities are from the rural area.

This analysis shows the importance of spatial location (NUTS 2 and NUTS 3 levels) in differentiation of white spots of EU funding. As EU funding policy mainly rests on development indicators as GDP per capita at NUTS 2 level, the study can prove a comprehensive lens on regional differences on white spots of EU funding in Romania.

Additional lines of statistical significant differences have been identified in relation to fiscal capacity, population dynamics, EU funding in previous programming period, State Budgets funding, level of development and being part of a functional urban area (FUA).

Map 1. White spots on EU funding

Rural municipalities with the lowest levels of EU funds absorption (including cases of localities with zero funds) from Romania tend to be to a significantly higher extent from the South development region of Romania.

On the opposite, the rural municipalities with the highest level of EU funds absorption are more likely to be located in Center, North-West, South West and West development regions. Compared to the EU-27 average, only the development region of Bucharest-Ilfov is above the EU-27 average.¹⁴ In this respect, the lowest value is registered for the development region of North-East, followed by South, South-West and South-East (data for 2019). Consequently, the highest values¹⁵ of GDP per capita are for the regions of West, North-West and Center. Therefore, the highest levels of EU funds absorption are associated with some of the highest levels of GDP per capita, with the exception of South-West region.

Nevertheless, the development region of Bucharest-Ilfov, which registers the highest GDP per capita, presents contrasting characteristics. tends to also be associated with cases of 'white spots' on EU funding. Cases of communes that did not absorb any EU funding are to a statistically higher extent from the development region of Bucharest-Ilfov. For a nuanced interpretation, it is important to mention that we examine only the role of rural municipalities in this paper and, notwithstanding, the development level of the entire region is associated with the capital city, not covered by this analysis. Additionally, cases of white spots from the rural area tend to be from the South development region, as already mentioned.

Map 2. Distribution of volume of EU funds among rural municipalities

¹⁴ Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant in percentage of the EU27 (from 2020) average, Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices by NUTS 2 regions [NAMA_10R_2GDP], Eurostat database.

¹⁵ With the exception of Bucharest-Ilfov region.

Table 3. Characteristics of the volume of EU funds absorption for the rural municipalities in Romania

		Volume of EU funds from 2014-2020 programming period					
		Zero funding	Lower quartile	Medium – low quartile	Medium – upper quartile	Upper quartile	Total
Fiscal capacity	Lower quartile	14.2	14.5	29.7	22.0	19.7	100
	Medium-low quartile	12.7	8.5	27.5	25.0	26.4	100
	Medium-upper quartile	14.4	8.7	25.1	23.9	27.9	100
	Upper quartile	20.7	8.9	17.7	22.5	30.1	100
Development Region	Bucharest -Ilfov	78.1	*	*	*	*	100
	Center	6.2	8.1	22.1	28.3	35.3	100
	North-East	14.8	12.6	23.1	27.9	21.5	100
	North-West	8.2	9.4	22.6	23.8	36.0	100
	South	26.0	13.5	30.6	17.7	12.1	100
	South-East	16.6	10.7	28.2	22.0	22.5	100
	South-West	11.0	7.6	29.2	22.1	30.1	100
	West	15.3	7.5	21.0	24.6	31.7	100
EU funding in previous programming period 2007-2013 (in 2016-2021)	No	16.9	11.3	27.9	22.7	21.2	100
	Yes	10.7	7.5	18.5	25.1	38.2	100
Population Dynamics in 2021 compared to 2014	Decrease by more than 10%	21.5	7.7	30.6	19.3	20.9	100
	Decrease by less than 10%	14.3	10.6	26.6	23.4	25.0	100
	No change or increase	14.5	10.7	18.8	25.4	30.5	100
Presence of a marginalized community	No	15.7	9.9	25.4	23.6	25.4	100
	Yes	14.4	11.1	25.4	22.9	26.2	100
Part of a Functional Urban Area (FUA)	No	15	10.4	26	22.8	25.8	100
	Yes	20.3	8.3	12.8	33.8	24.8	100
With State Budget Funding	No	21.6	10.6	26.5	19.7	21.6	100
	Yes	14.6	10.2	25.3	23.7	26.1	100
Level of Development	Developed	14.9	11.1	20.0	27.7	26.3	100
	Getting out of poverty	19.8	7.4	26.8	20.8	25.2	100
	In stagnating poverty	13.0	11.7	30	20.5	24.9	100
	Dynamic average developed	15.9	8.5	27.6	23.1	24.9	100
	Stagnating average developed	11.3	10.5	22.6	26.6	29.0	100
	Higher average dynamic developed	18.3	10.3	22.1	20.6	28.6	100
	Missing information	20.7	10.3	15.2	31.7	22.1	100
	Total (%)	15.3	10.3	25.4	23.3	25.7	100
	Total (N)	437	294	727	668	736	2862

Source: Author's calculations. Grey cells indicate significantly higher values (adjusted residuals). * Less than 5 cases.

If we consider a more disaggregated level, at county level (NUTS 3 level), the communes placed in the upper quartile of EU funds absorption, are more likely to be from the counties of Bistrița-Năsăud, Cluj, Harghita, Hunedoara, Mureș and Tulcea. From this set of counties, only Cluj¹⁶ has the highest GDP per capita (after Bucharest) in Romania. The rest of mentioned counties, Bistrița-Năsăud, Harghita, Hunedoara, Mureș and Tulcea range under this indicator from 15,500 (Bistrița-Năsăud) to 17,400 (Hunedoara).

At county level, the communes placed in the lowest quartile of EU funds absorption (still different from the ones lacking EU funding) tend to be from the counties of Bacău, Dâmbovița, Galați, Neamț, Satu Mare, Sibiu.¹⁷ In what concerns the case of white spots from the rural area, a previous analysis shows they tend to be from a higher extent from the counties of Argeș, Brăila, Constanța, Giurgiu, Ialomița, Ilfov and Vaslui (Marin et al., 2022).

Adding on, if we complete the picture at NUTS3 level with a composite index on the territorial quality of life index, we see that, on the contrary to the GDP/capita measure, we have Hunedoara and Bistrița-Năsăud counties on higher values than for instance Cluj county. Nevertheless, when reading these results, it is important to consider that at NUTS 0 level, in the European context, Romania as a whole is placed in a low position (ESPON, 2016).

Contrary to the expected relationship, there is no statistical significant correlation between categories measuring EU funds level absorption and typology of rural marginalized communities. Several possible lines of explanation can be put forward here. On the one hand, the presence of a marginalized community has been taken into consideration in several EU funding lines. Adding on, these marginalized communities partially overlap with the presence of disadvantaged communities, as in the case of for instance disadvantaged schools in the Operational Program for Human Capital (POCU 2014-2020). However, this does not mean that it is for sure that the funds absorbed by the municipalities including this type of communities have actually been spent for them. This question can only be tested if information at a more disaggregated level is available, namely at village level (SIRUTA inferior). An example of this type of analysis conducted for the projects funded from Romania's largest State Budget Program (PNDL2)¹⁸ is available in Marin, 2021.

Communes placed in the upper average quartile of EU funds absorption (but not the highest quartile) tend to be from developed communes, where development is measured based on the index computed by professor Dumitru Sandu. In addition, communes from the lower average quartile are in a 'stagnating poverty' category.

Levels of EU funds absorption for the rural area tend to be in an ambivalent relationship with the degree of financial autonomy. We have computed indicators on financial capacity as a mean

¹⁶ Cluj county has a value of 29,800 (Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant. Eurostat database, Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices by NUTS 3 regions [NAMA_10R_3GDP].

¹⁷ In the case of Brasov county there are less than 10 counties.

¹⁸ National Program for Local Development, one of the largest State Budget funded programs.

average for the first three available years (2016, 2017 and 2018) in constant euro 2010 per inhabitant as well as shares of own revenues in the total revenues. In the case of financial capacity measured in constant euro 2010 per inhabitant, communes from the highest quartile of EU funds absorption tend also to be from the highest quartile of fiscal capacity. Yet, communes without EU funds in this programming period tend to be from the highest quartile of EU funding. The relationship with the white spots on EU funding holds true even if we compute the fiscal capacity as a share of own revenues in total revenues. It might be a better solution to compute the fiscal capacity also considering the years of 2014 and 2015 as starting points for the examined programming period, yet this has not been the case for our study.

EU funds absorption in the previous programming period is relevant for the level of absorption in the next one, namely 2014-2020, the one examined in this paper. The ones placed in the lower and in the average lower quartile of EU funds absorption in 2014-2020 are to a significantly larger extent from the ones without funds or projects in implementation from the previous programming period. Communes from the upper quartile are also more likely to have projects in implementation. A previous analysis (Marin et al., 2022) shows that white spots in the current programming period tend to be from communes without EU funding in the previous programming period. In addition, regarding relationships with the urban areas, communes from the medium upper quartile are more likely to be part of a functional urban area. "A functional urban area consists of a city and its commuting zone. Functional urban areas therefore consist of a densely inhabited city and a less densely populated commuting zone whose labour market is highly integrated with the city".¹⁹

Adding on, rural localities placed in the upper quartile of EU funds absorption are from communes with no change or even increase of population between 2021 and 2014. On the contrary, current white spots tend to be from communes with a decrease by more than 10 percent of population in the same timeframe. Further to this, size of the population registered at Census matters. Communes in the average lower quartile tend to be from rural municipalities up to 5,000 inhabitants. For a correct interpretation of this data, it is worthwhile mentioning that the way the absorption capacity and therefore placement in various quartile has been computed takes into consideration the locality population from each of the analyzed year (at euro in constant 2010 prices per inhabitant) and, therefore, not the population registered at the latest available Census.

6. Discussion

The results of the analysis highlight the importance of the territorial dimension when studying distribution of EU funds, as preceding research have also revealed, at different territorial levels of analysis (Capello, 2018, Collins et al., 2017, Hochholdinger et al., 2021, Kalfova, 2019, Komorowski et al., 2021, Maier et al., 2021, Milio, 2007, Nicholas, 2021, Weber, 2020). The objective of reducing regional inequalities is an intrinsic part of the EU's aims towards promoting economic, social and

¹⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Functional_urban_area.

territorial cohesion (Article 174 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union). Same article mentions a particular attention paid to rural areas and regions affected by “severe and permanent natural or demographic handicaps”.²⁰

Affiliation to a specific development region (NUTS2) or county (NUTS 3) differentiates the volume of absorbed EU funds. Although, as stated earlier, development regions are only statistical constructs, their importance in differentiation of absorbed EU funds for the municipalities placed in the rural area has been proven by this study. The importance of development regions will grow even more in the upcoming years as for the next programming period, 2021-2027, the programming of regional operational programs is specific for each development region.²¹ However, the coordination of implementation of this regional level programs is not placed with a local public authority in Romania. Instead, at the regional level, intermediate level organisations in the systems of EU funding are represented by the regional development agencies, which represent structures organized similar to non-governmental organizations. Additionally, although the study did not study the quality of governance or other structural characteristics at regional level, the differentiation by this type of territory is in line with the studies of Kersan-Škabić, Tijanić, L., 2017 and Kalfova, 2019. For Romania’s case, the longitudinal clusterization at NUTS 3 level, from East to West is partially confirmed, but the two studies are not directly comparable. Our study takes into consideration the whole volume of funds, while the one previously conducted for Romania only analyzes the funds from the Common Agricultural Policy (Maier et al., 2022). In our study, the counties from which rural municipalities with the highest volume of funds are more likely to come from, are indeed closer to the Western part of the country, with the exception of Tulcea. Tulcea county presents in itself a special case as it is both a border county, as well as a special program for developing local communities from the Danube Delta (integrated territorial intervention – ITI Danube Delta, placed in the South East development region). The rest of the counties identified by the current analysis, Bistrița-Năsăud, Cluj, Harghita and Hunedoara are located in the North-West, West and Center development regions.

Adding on, size of the budget and level of development also count in differentiation of EU funding levels, in line with earlier research (Cyburt, 2014, Komorowski et al., 2021, Marin, 2014, Mirska, 2021), or issues related to the demographic decline present in a part of the examined rural areas, as has been already pointed out in Weber et al., 2020. The importance of previous lack of experience with EU funding in the case of ‘white spots’ is in line with earlier research for the earlier programming period, again in reference mostly to rural municipalities.

Notwithstanding, EU funding policy has been several times advocated as one important pillar in addressing the needs of rural shrinkage areas (Weber et al., 2020). This study explicitly addresses this topic and opens up the debate for a similar analysis at the EU level. The analysed database

²⁰ OECD definition on Eurostat, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:12008E174&from=EN>.

²¹ In the present time (December 2, 2022) four regional development programs are approved by the European Commission – for the development regions of North-West, South, South-West and West, <https://mfe.gov.ro/programe-regionale-21-27/>.

provides an improved integration of all sources of EU funding, although a differentiation between funding lines would be able to render a more nuanced picture on this topic.

7. Conclusions and next steps

Spatial attributes like development region and county affiliation of a commune differentiate levels of EU funds absorption. Furthermore, financial capacity, affiliation to a functional urban area, demographic decline, population size, State budget funds or EU funds absorption in the previous programming period also account for statistical significant differences in the rural municipality capacity to attract EU funds during 2014-2020 programming period. In Romania, rural municipalities with higher levels of absorbed volume of EU funding are to a statistically higher extent from the development regions of Center, North-West, South West and West, from communes with no change or even increase of population between 2021 and 2014, from the highest quartile of fiscal capacity, with previous experience on EU funding in the preceding programming period. They are too more likely to be from the counties of Bistrița-Năsăud, Cluj, Harghita, Hunedoara, Mureș and Tulcea. Adding on, communes from the medium upper quartile of EU funding tend to be from developed communes, part of a functional urban area and from the development regions of Center and North-East. As all the data from the analyzed programming period (2014-2020) will become available from the same information source (local budgets execution reports), it is possible that these characteristics/ grouping can yield different results. Moreover, it would be good to have a finer picture on the different allocations of EU funding based mainly on NUTS 2 dimension, in order to have an improved contextualization of results. It can be the case that this criterion would become more pronounced for the programming period of 2021-2027, as part of the EU funds are allocated in Romania through individual regional operational programs.

The study's results are based on an extensive database including all available information on EU funding (2016-2021) for all the rural municipalities in Romania. Consequently, its results can serve as a reliable source of information, which can, however, be altered as update on EU funding at the municipality's level will become available through the next local budgets execution reports. Notwithstanding, the latest population Census conducted across the EU can better inform on the diverse characteristics, challenges and needs that rural areas across the EU experience, especially after the pandemic period as well as the currently unfolding war in Ukraine, coupled with increasing energy tariffs. On the side, a qualitative approach on the motivations for (not) entering EU funds competition and/ or the 'soft side' of the internal organizational structure of 'success' municipalities can bring about new insights with relevant experience for both academic and practitioners fields.

This article adds to the growing knowledge on territorial evidence and can be further used as a policy instrument in order to closer examine the intervention tools from the EU funding policy.

The final results from the examined programming period can provide a different picture. Even under these circumstances, the paper can be used as a way to explore an improved coordination of policy interventions that ultimately benefit a larger spectrum of rural areas. The open database and the study's analyses represent a plea for on the one hand, replicate the methodology in other EU countries, especially on rural areas, and, on the other hand, use the available data as an extensive case-study (with almost 3,000 localities) in one member state for which EU funding has only recently been available. In a systemic approach, the results of the analysis are valuable for design of integrated place-based strategies for EU, national and local level stakeholders, having as ultimate goal an improved quality of life for citizens living in rural areas.

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Annex

Table 4. List of variables